

A PLANT FIGHTING AGAINST CANCER

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Abstract: Glycyrrhiza glabra, also known as licorice, has been widely used in medicine for 6000 years. Its roots have a long history in Western countries for their aromatic scent, anti-inflammatory properties, and calming effects. Additionally, Glycyrrhiza glabra roots contain various substances such as alkaloids, glycosides, starches, phenolic compounds, proteins, lipids, and flavonoids. Furthermore, it possesses numerous pharmacological effects, including memory enhancement, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, anticancer, and many others.

Looking back, our people extensively utilized plants in medicine and turned to them as sources of health. In today's developing countries, the demand for natural pharmaceuticals is constantly increasing, and many individuals seek natural plant-based medicines. Humans have used plants for medicinal purposes for centuries. Licorice has been known as a valuable medicinal plant since ancient times. Its roots contain a plethora of biologically active substances, while its aerial parts have been found to contain tannins and essential oils. Moreover, this plant is one of the most popular in China.

This article aims to identify the medicinal properties of licorice and investigate the anticancer properties of its roots.

Description

Licorice is a perennial plant belonging to the legume family, reaching a height of 50-100 cm with well-developed underground parts. Its stem is smooth and quite tall. The strong, branched root system reaches a depth of 5 meters and produces

lateral shoots. New plants emerge from these shoots in spring, leading to the formation of entire thickets of licorice. A characteristic feature of the leaves is not only their shape but also their sticky underside. It blooms with small, light purple flowers gathered in a brush. The seeds ripen in smooth, flat, dark brown pods.

Due to its chemical composition, this plant has cosmetic, medicinal, and industrial applications. It contains various types of sugars:

- * Polysaccharides
- * Organic acids
- * Essential oils
- * Fats, carbohydrates
- * Vitamins
- * Flavonoids

Medicinal Uses

In medicine, licorice, also known as Glycyrrhiza, is used for its various benefits. Its roots contain healing substances similar to steroid hormones, providing a distinct anti-inflammatory effect. These substances enhance the body's resistance to pathogens.

In folk medicine, licorice root decoction is used as an expectorant, emollient, and anti-inflammatory agent for respiratory diseases such as chest pain, cough, and whooping cough. It is also used as a mild laxative for gastrointestinal disorders, a diuretic, and a remedy for thirst and shortness of breath. Glycyram, extracted from the root, is used to treat asthma, allergies, eczema, and licorice extract is used to treat stomach and duodenal ulcers. Finely chopped licorice root is widely used for respiratory diseases.

Licorice has been used in folk medicine since ancient times. It is mentioned in the Chinese "Book of Plants" and was classified as a first-class medicinal plant by Chinese physicians. Licorice is widely used to treat respiratory diseases

accompanied by a strong cough with thick sputum. Decoctions and infusions of the plant help relieve nausea and improve digestion.

Licorice is very beneficial for men and is often used in combination with other herbs to treat prostate adenoma. Consuming licorice improves immunity and reduces the risk of contracting diseases from pathogens. The antitumor effect of licorice root is utilized to prevent the development of prostate tumors.

Conclusion

This article highlights the potential of licorice as a natural remedy for various ailments, including cancer. The research suggests that licorice possesses numerous beneficial properties, warranting further investigation to explore its full medicinal potential and develop standardized treatment protocols.

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